

CUSTOMIZABLE CATEGORIZATION OF DOCUMENTS IN EVIDENCE-BASED RESEARCH FOR BIO PHARMACEUTICS

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Abstract

This paper describes a strategy that combines bottom-up topic extraction and personalized expert category classification to facilitate evidence-based research in drug development within the bio pharmaceuticals field. Bio pharmaceutical scientists spend a significant portion of their time and effort looking for information and establishing relationships with existing scientific outcomes. Through evidence-based research, they seek to find published scientific studies towards answering a clinical question. While language models can assist with topic extraction, their specificity may not match expert categorization. To address this, the paper introduces the Health Optimization Tool (HOT), which combines personalized document classification with topic extraction. HOT allows scientists to train the document classifier according to their specific needs, leveraging the strengths of both approaches. The system offers a unified user interface with document and category overviews, enabling graphical or query-based searches. Using a personalized classifier on top of a language model enables the possibility of interactively updating the classification while retaining the strength of the topic extraction. The paper includes a proof of concept, detailing the creation of the database, fine-tuning of the language model, and preliminary study with experts.

INTRODUCTION

The ability to analyze and organize large collections of information, to draw relations between pieces of evidence is paramount to build knowledge. In the health related domains, Evidence-Based Research (EBR, also evidence-based medicine) refers to informing clinical or medical inquiries through the systematic and transparent use of prior research [7]. It is an ethical question. On the one hand, unnecessary research puts patients at avoidable risks. On the other hand, a requirement of replicability necessarily implies the identification of prior research. Hereby, experts screen articles from biomedical journals, usually accessible through online databases like PubMed, for example seeking concrete studies on topics like patient populations, diagnosis, treatments, adverse cases, and effects of public policies in medicine [8]. In the pharmaceutical sector, specifically in drug development, this task entails comprehensive retrieval of sources and organizing them based on provided categories for expert analysis.

Language models capture the use of language structures across a variety of linguistic contexts [15]. A language model supports NLP tasks such as named entity recognition, sentiment analysis or text classification [21]. For example, biomedical NLP has been successfully used for identification of diseases [20,21], identification of sound treatment studies [13,14], or classification according to medical concepts [18]. A common approach is to start from a pre-trained large language model, such as ELMO [15], BERT [9], BioBERT [12], XLNet [11] and fine-tune towards the desired task. However, identifying the right model for a task is not trivial [21]. Besides, language models still struggle with certain domain-specific terminology [16], and new or adapted vocabularies hinder generalization. Finally, experts may focus on different needs depending the background and goals, and classification of a document may differ. A more flexible approach is required.

Numerous tools using interactive exploration techniques [2–5] have been developed with the objective of assisting users in exploring relevant content; However, a notable limitation of these existing tools is their focus on a specific domain, which results in restricting their applicability across diverse domains. Additionally, the absence of customization options hinders users from tailoring the default classifier to suit their specific needs and preferences. For example, PubVis [2] is an interactive tool designed to facilitate the exploration and discovery of scientific publications. PubVis focuses on the interactive exploration and discovery of scientific publications through visualization and does not offer a customized classification however it provides users with personalized content-based article recommendations. Another example is Thalia [3] which is designed to assist researchers in retrieving relevant information from vast collections of biomedical abstracts by utilizing semantic search capabilities. Thalia leverages advanced natural language processing techniques to understand the context and meaning of the query terms, enabling more accurate and comprehensive search results. One recent contributions to the document screening and exploration methods is Carvallo et al [5] which presents a novel method for automatic document screening in the medical domain. The suggested approach shows potential in enhancing the efficiency and accuracy of screening operations, alleviating the load of manual screening, and enabling researchers to stay up to date with the newest medical literature by leveraging word and text embedding combined with active learning techniques.

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APPROACH

The context of this work is a customized document classification system for the pharmaceutical industry that aims to make it easier for chemists, pharmaceutical professionals, and medical researchers to access the medical literature they need. Users expect the system to categorize documents in accordance with categories they (or the organization) have provided or defined. This section consists of 1) System Architecture, 2) User Interface, 3) Classification, and 4) Topic Modeling sub-sections.

System Architecture

The main system architecture is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The system architecture of the tool: A BERTopic model is trained and used to categorize new documents in the tool’s back-end using the input data that is taken from PubMed. In the front-end, a graphical user interface displays the data and offers interactive exploration options for users.

The Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)¹ are the categories used by the prototype here. Users may assign documents to several categories in hoping to improve classification since categories are frequently defined in a vague manner.

User Interface

The user interface of the tool can be observed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The tool’s user interface including the graphical document classification, document table, and the search bar

The tool’s source code is initially implemented in HTML and D3 JavaScript for the user interface, and in Python for

models. Mongo DB is utilized to store both the extracted topics and data from PubMed and output results; Whereas JSON files are used to represent all other default data, such as category headings and their hierarchical structure. The tool’s user interface consists of three main sections: a search bar, a graph with the titles of all the categories, and a document list. The search bar can be used by users to perform a search query. The table of search results shows the topics and categories that the documents were sorted into. Additionally, linked categories containing the entered topic highlight upon entry. If a category title is entered in the search bar, the graph will automatically zoom into that category and the results table shows the documents related to that category (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Enter the category title in the search bar to zoom into a specific category. The document table is also updated accordingly. The subjects displayed in the selected category are the five most-relevant topics to the category discovered in all associated papers to the selected category. The numbers on the bar charts show the frequency with which the topic appears within the category.

Topic Modeling

For extracting topics from text data, the topic modeling method BERTopic [6] is used. This method makes use of transformers and the c-TF-IDF (contrastive term frequency-inverse document frequency) algorithm to pinpoint the terms that occur most frequently in a particular text corpus. Document clustering is another service provided by BERTopic based on the identified themes. The method also offers the opportunity to train BERTopic models using labeled datasets, allowing us to categorize the documents using the trained BERTopic model by annotated content.

To apply BERTopic in a supervised manner to a dataset, as shown in Diagram 4, a collection of publications containing class labels is obtained by crawling the Pubmed² database. These labels correspond to the MeSH headlines.

¹ MeSH, Available online: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mesh>

² Pubmed, Available online: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>

Although MeSH contains multiple levels of headlines and sub-headings, for the purpose of this study, only two levels are considered, resulting in the extraction of 47 headlines and sub-headings from MeSH.

Figure 4: The tool’s back-end, BERTopic, labels the dataset

For the document dataset, a dedicated crawler is configured for each category, extracting a set of 1000 documents per category. These documents consist of the publication abstract, author details, paper link, and a label indicating the corresponding MeSH category. In the next step, an additional set of 10,000 documents is crawled using a separate crawler, regardless of their MeSH headline. Topics are extracted using the same BERTopic model trained in the first phase. The model is configured to select and store the 10 best features according to their probability of frequency for each document. The topics are then vectorized, along with their corresponding probabilities.

The BERTopic model’s performance on topic reduction for a total number of 10000 documents is tested using two clustering methods of UMAP and HDBSCAN. The results can be observed in Table 1.

Table 1: BERTopic topic reduction results

N neighbors	MinTopicSize	clusters
UMAP	HDBSCAN	
200	150	3 random noise
100	75	7 random noise
50	35	11 random noise
35	30	28 random noise
30	25	50 random noise
25	18	78 random noise

Classification

The tool can be configured to employ all kinds of textual data, but in order to develop the classification model, it first needs a list of default headlines and subheadings in at least two levels and tagged documents. We chose medical records as our use case.

For the document classification, a similarity matrix is used to evaluate the relative score of different classes (categories) in respect to the topics extracted from each distinct document.

Therefore, for each document, a similarity matrix $M_{i,j}$ (Matrix 1) including all extracted topics and the probabilities of that topic appearing in all existing classes(categories) is created as the following, where each row represents a topic and each column represents a class. Therefore, $M_{i,j}$ is a 10×47 matrix, where $P_{i,c}$ indicates the similarity between features for the feature i appearing in the class c .

$$M_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{0,0} & p_{0,1} & \dots & p_{0,46} \\ p_{1,0} & p_{1,1} & \dots & p_{1,46} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ p_{9,0} & p_{9,1} & \dots & p_{9,46} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

In order to detect the highly related categories to each document, $p_{doc,c}$, the word embedding similarity scores in each column are summed up (Equation 2) to find the highest values for each class. $p_{doc,c}$ indicates the probability of a category being related to a document.

$$p_{doc,c} = \sum_{i=0}^9 p_{i,c} \quad (2)$$

In the next step, n number of the classes with the highest values are selected for that document. The system chooses the categories with the greatest values as the most related categories to the document by creating a list of all probabilities for the document belonging to each category Cat_{doc_i} .

$$Cat_{doc_i} = Max[p_{doc_i,c_0}, \dots, p_{doc_i,c_{46}}] \quad (3)$$

Documents are then labeled according to the values of the list 3 and the results are stored in the database.

EXPERT STUDY

The evaluation of our approach involves: 1) assessing the user experience and 2) evaluating the accuracy of topic modeling and 3) of document classification.

User experience

A number of tasks have been designed to evaluate the user interface, drawing inspiration from actual situations that mimic the actions taken by pharmaceutical experts in their search for certain information. Participants had to complete these predetermined assignments and find the answers to the corresponding questions. The users were instructed to perform separate searches for each topic listed in the "Topic" column of Table 5 and complete the table. They were asked to explore the tool’s interface freely and intuitively while conducting their searches, and to verbally express their thought process. Verbal responses were recorded along with the computer screen.

As an example of their tasks they were asked to use the tool to investigate common symptoms of COVID-19 in children and to print their final results. They had the option to simultaneously search for multiple topics and explore the results section. Additionally, they were instructed to utilize the tool to research changes in the brain associated with Alzheimer’s disease and print their final results. Similar to

TOPIC	Total number of categories including the topic	Names of all categories including the topic	Total number of sub-categories including the topic	Names of all sub-categories including the topic. Please, add information on the frequency of the topic within each sub-category in brackets, e.g., diseases (13).
animal				
virus				
infants				

Figure 5: A sample of the designed tasks for user experiments.

the previous task, they were allowed to conduct multiple simultaneous searches and explore the results section.

As shown in Figure 2, 12 classes represent the main (parent) categories and the rest are sub-categories of the main classes. In this study, the customized version of the tool was designed to address a specific purpose, tailored to the needs of domain experts in a particular department of the target pharmaceutical company. Due to the limited number of domain experts who would be utilizing this tool with the customized data, our user study consisted of only three participants. Despite the limited sample size, it is significant to note that these individuals have a high level of domain expertise, making them valuable contributors.

Figure 6 summarizes the means of users rankings in Visual Analogue Scales (VAS) ³ for each existing features within the tool. Users' feedback indicated that the existing features and the graph representation of the tool were found useful by all participants. However, some users encountered difficulties in interacting with the tool, except for the user who had close involvement in the development process. The provision of a manual guide was highly appreciated by the users, as it enhanced the usability of the tool. Additionally, offering various solutions for navigation through the graph, such as using the mouse wheel, was considered very beneficial by the users.

Usability of existing features:	Raw Mean
Graphical overview of (sub-) categories and topics	78.33333333
Document list overview	71.66666667
Search button alternatives	55
Topic categorization (i.e., in-graph categories and sub-categories)	75.33333333
Visualization and overview of top five topics per sub-category	68
Bar chart information on the total number of topics within each sub-category	61.33333333
One-page (as opposed to multiple-pages) user interface	66.33333333
Highlighting sub-categories including the searched (i.e., entered) topic	79.66666667
Search result download	85.66666667
Search query entering options	82.33333333
Navigation between (sub-) categories	53
Colours of the graph background	62

Figure 6: Summarized means scores of the visual analogue scales (VASs) usability of existing features

Topic modeling

For the identified topics, participants were asked to review the abstracts associated with each task and evaluate the

³ Visual Analogue Scales, Available online: https://www.physio-pedia.com/Visual_Analogue_Scale

accuracy of the detected topics compared to their conventional search method which is through public search engines (e.g., PubMed). In the user study, 100 randomly labeled documents were selected from each category, amounting to a total of 1000 documents per category. These documents were reviewed by a knowledgeable practitioner. It was found that approximately 10 percent of the documents showed only marginal relevance to their assigned classes while the rest were highly relevant. An expert reviewer was then tasked with going through the database and finding any documents that had been incorrectly categorized. No mislabelled documents were reported by the expert reviewer as a result of the document classes being closely related to one another. The assessment study did, however, point out that numerous documents had just a slight relevance to the classes they were allocated, suggesting the possibility for improvement. It had been proposed that adding more precise classes to the category hierarchy might improve the classification. Deeper classes provide a more precise assignment of extracted topics from each document to their own focused classes by making the boundaries between categories across the entire database more clearly defined.

Document classification

Participants were asked to assess the binary probability of the assigned category for each document, indicating whether it is "relevant" or "irrelevant" by assessing the final obtained search results from the experiments and comparing them with similar search results from the PubMed database. Compared to searching through other databases, evaluation findings showed that users could obtain relevant results for the target category significantly more quickly. However, due to the database's small quantity of documents, it was not always possible to find all the relevant material that users were looking for.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In the subsequent stage, our research aims to assess the efficacy of the customized classification module, wherein users have the possibility to upload batches of 100 labeled documents per category. This process enables users to fine-tune the classification of each category according to their specific requirements and preferences. For instance, users can exclude a broad range of sub-categories and shift the focus of a category towards more relevant ones.

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